
Identifying the Advantages of Task-Based Language Teaching

G.Kavitha, MA, Don Bosco College (Co-Ed)

Sarath Kumar. G, MA, Assistant Professor

Paper Received on 15-08-2023, Accepted on 21-09-2023,
Published on 22-09-23; DOI: 10.36993/ RJOE.2023.8.3.257

Abstract:

There has been a lot of research on how a second language can be taught effectively in the language classroom. This research paper is going to explore the advantages of using task-based language teaching in the process of second language learning. Task-based language teaching (TBLT) is an approach that includes teaching sessions and materials formed based on completing a task. This approach has been implemented to teach language successfully since the early 1980s. In this process, the learners do not depend on rules of grammar or memorizing lists of vocabulary of the target language. Instead, they are made to communicate in the target language through which they learn the target language. The primary focus of language learning is observing the form and the meaning cooperatively. TBLT allows the learners to acquire linguistics and sociolinguistics skills while performing the task. The research suggests that TBLT is one of the best teaching methods for second language learning.

Keywords: task, teaching sessions, materials, form, meaning

Task-based language teaching (TBLT) is an approach that includes teaching sessions and materials formed based on completing a task. This approach has been implemented to teach language successfully since the early 1980s. The cause for the success of this real approach is that it centers on the meaning rather than the form. Task-based language teaching or task-based instruction was formed by the educators because they want the learners to express meanings and also to make the language classroom completely communicative. Ellis (2003) defines tasks as “tasks are activities that call for primarily meaning-focused language use” (3). TBLT was first established by NS Prabhu, Bangalore, India. The concept of task-based language learning is developed from a well-known model called communicative language teaching.

Task-based learning is not a new method. Rather, it simply puts the task at the center of one's methodological focus. It views the learning process as a set of communicative tasks that are directly linked to the curricular goals they serve, the purposes of which extend beyond the practice of language for its own sake. Research on task-based learning attempts to identify types of tasks that enhance learning (for example, open-ended, structured,

teacher-fronted, small group, and pair work) and to define task-specific learner factors (roles, proficiency levels, styles), teacher roles, and other variables that contribute to successful achievement of goals (Brown 83)

There has been a lot of research on how a second language can be taught effectively in the language classroom. This research paper is going to explore the advantages of using task-based language teaching in the process of second language learning. In the process of completing a given task, the learners are made to use the second language. In this process, the learners do not depend on rules of grammar or memorizing lists of vocabulary of the target language. Instead, they are made to communicate in the target language through which they learn the target language.

TBLT provides suitable circumstances for the learners to bring out meaningful and natural communication. It helps them to increase their fluency and confidence. The tasks are usually given to fit into the naturalistic framework with a specific outcome. Skehan explains, "A task is an activity that satisfies the following criteria: meaning is primary, there is a goal that needs to be worked forward, the activity is outcome-evaluated, and there is a real-

world relationship" (Celce-Murcia and Olshtain, 189). In the TBLT class, learners can either work alone to complete a task, or they can do the task by working as a group.

Individual task:

- Explaining a way to the hospital
- Creating a new letter
- Designing a map of the house
- Solving a problem.

Group activity:

- Organizing an event
- Attending an interview or conducting an interview
- Participating in a debate
- Performing role-play or games.

Students are likely to participate in task-based activities with substantial motivation. It also provides them with circumstances to exhibit their skills and also to upskill themselves. Learners, while working as a team, are able to create meaningful communication based on the given task. Along with language learning, the process also provides the learner with knowledge and experience. Learners from all ages and different backgrounds can use the TBLT model for language learning. The task given in the classroom is based on the needs aim. It is also befitting the learner's level of proficiency in the target language.

For beginners:	Advanced level:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task with specific input and output • Arrange visual aids and models. • Provide direct guidance and instructions. • Decrease the time limit and the task's scope. • Make positive feedback. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enlarge the input and output of the language. • Arrange fewer visual aids and models. • Provide questionable guidance and instruction. • Increase the time limit and the task's scope. • Make less positive feedback.

The primary focus of language learning is observing the form and the meaning cooperatively. Though it's a great challenge to obtain them equally at the same time, to learn the target language, it is necessary to balance fluency and accuracy. Learning a second language through TBLT paves the way for balancing between fluency and accuracy. To focus on the form is not the predominant attention of TBLT. The process makes the learners acquire form easily. Particularly when the learners move from easy tasks to the advanced level, learners are able to acquire linguistic elements of the target language. Thus, TBLT allows the learners to acquire linguistics and sociolinguistics skills while

performing the task. The research suggests that TBLT is one of the best teaching methods for second language learning.

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How to cite this article?

G.Kavitha, "Identifying the Advantages of Task-Based Language Teaching" *Research Journal Of English (RJOE)*8(3), PP:255-257,2023, DOI:10.36993/RJOE.2023.8.3.257